

MULTIPLE CASE STUDY ANALYSIS

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ORGANISATION DEVELOPMENT AND CHANGE

by

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Abstract

This research paper is discussing on various theories relating to the knowledge economy. There are various perspectives about the relationship of knowledge management (KM) with organisational performance. Knowledge plays a role as the critical resource in an organisation. However, it is the proper management of knowledge that enables organisations to enhance their competitiveness. To look at the effectiveness of the theory, three case studies has been analysed and compared. These three case studies share a common issue, that is, the proper management of knowledge. This paper is discussing the issues and then providing alternative solutions to the problems. The recommendation includes having the right skills, relevant knowledge and retaining the key employees. Besides that, it is also recommended to employ the skilled workers from an established organisation or engaging a consultant. To improve the organisations, various strategies were recommended.

1 Problem Statement

Three case studies were given to be analysed. The first case study is about **Sumbiling Eco Village (SEV): Promoting the Ecotourism in the Temburong District**. Though they have properly implemented their promotion strategies, they have other problems that includes maintaining and repairing materials that were eroding due to the weather, shortage of skilled workers who are crucial to maintaining and sustaining the SEV mission, their competition from other nearby outbound retreats, and also, there is the situation of an increase in visitors that could lead to environment degradation. In case study two, it is about **BruTEL's 'Going Paperless' Initiative**, where the dilemmas found were that there was still a percentage of users who are less receptive of this change particularly senior citizens, the customers' password fatigue, and the cumbersome enrolment process. Lastly, in case study three, it is about **Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT)'s Green Xchange Project**. The major challenge they faced was funding's. They had difficulty in securing funding's, which is used for them to further improve and expand its existing corporate social responsibilities (CSR) projects.

Based on the three case studies above, it was found that there was no proper management of the organisational knowledge. For that, this paper is finding alternative solutions on how the to leverage and strengthen the knowledge for an effective organisational performance.

2 Case Analysis

2.1 General Background of OD

There are several definitions of OD, but to summarise them, OD leads to organisation effectiveness that uses the application and transfer of behavioral science knowledge to the planned development, improvement, and reinforcement of strategic, structures, and process (Cummings & Worley, 2009). In today's society, the pace of change of organisations and businesses have never been greater (Burnes, 2004; Kotter, 1996). According to Senge (1990), organisations who can either keep up or use the momentum of the change process will be able to survive and possibly thrive.

Unlike change programs that usually focuses on one or a few aspects of the system, OD applies to changes in the strategy, structure, and processes of an entire system. The entire system can consist of an organisation, a single plant of a multi-plant firm, a department or work group, or individual role or job. So that the system is more capable of carrying out planned changes, OD distinguishes itself by showing its intent to transfer behavioral science knowledge, skill, and microconcepts such as leadership, group dynamics, and work designs, as well as macroapproaches such as strategy, organisation design, and international relations. As change is an inevitable feature for organisations, OD which is capable in carrying out planned changes, will be able to help organisations solve problems, learn from experience, reframe shared perceptions, adapt to external environmental changes, improve performance, and influence future changes.

The OD methods of intervention affects individuals, groups, and the organisation as a whole, and can be applied to each of these levels according to the degree they affect human processes (communication, decision-making, problem resolution, and leadership), techno-structures (type of designs, structure of tasks, and the level of delegation and formalisation), management of human resources (development of skills, modes of socialisation, and systems of promotion/rewards), and

strategy (positioning in the market, type of transactions with the environment, and the company culture as a tool for stakeholders). OD is critical to change in order to improve quality and effectiveness, and typically involves a dynamic complex interaction between those who, despite frustrations, are entangled to the present state, and those who share a vision for a better future.

2.2 Knowledge Management (KM)

Knowledge is becoming ever more important in today's economy and has been characterised as a major factor of production in the value-adding economic activities in this evolved economy known as the knowledge economy. Through understanding how people learn, relearn, and unlearn, the new economy has based itself on creating economic value (Kwon & Cho, 2016; Villasalero, 2014; Zhao et al., 2013). Knowledge resides in the brains of the employees which by leveraging the employees' knowledge, the organisation can develop various strategies to create organisational knowledge.

Recently, most business have been flooded with information that becomes too much for them to handle. Anthes (1998) states that KM is trying to resolve this difficult paradox. KM is referred to as a range of practices and techniques that are used by the organisation in order to identify, represent and distribute knowledge, expertise, know-hows, intellectual capital and other forms of knowledge for leverage, transfer and reuse of knowledge and learning across the organisation (Iandoli & Zollo, 2007). It is said that the concept of knowledge and KM is complex, as knowledge exists in the human mind, which cannot be communicated nor be easily understood by others as knowledge is more personalised and contextualised. It was then argued that, for a successful KM program, it does not only need to convert internalised tacit (subjective) knowledge into explicit codified knowledge (systematic or technical) to share it, but for also individuals and groups to internalise and personally make the knowledge their own once it is retrieved from the KM system (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995).

In Gold, Malhotra and Segars (2001) perspective of the organisational capabilities, they examined the issue of effective KM, where it suggests a knowledge infrastructure which is essential organisational capabilities or "preconditions" for effective KM. The knowledge infrastructure consists of structure, technology and culture, as well as knowledge process architecture of acquiring, converting, applying, and protecting. As an organisation enters a program of KM, the results provide a basis for understanding the competitive predisposition of the organisation.

Researchers have argued that there are several reasons that organisations are interested in managing knowledge, which includes the realisation that wealth is generated from knowledge and intangible assets, recognition that innovation stems from knowledge creation and application, rediscovery that human resource is the pool of organisational knowledge, competition and technology demands continuous learning to remain competitive, growing importance of cross-boundary knowledge transactions due to globalisation process, rapid changes occurring in the markets, and lastly, limitations that technology has in order to unearth certain types of knowledge such as tacit knowledge (Baker and Baker, 2001; Quintas, 2002). Bonner (2000) states that KM is an ongoing process within the organisational boundaries, which become cumulative when knowledge is shared within the organisation. In order to enhance organisational effectiveness, KM needs to be supported by the right kind of strategies, structures, system, culture and people management policies and practices, so as to codify tacit knowledge and utilising tacit as well as

explicit knowledge. To preserve and expand their core competencies, organisations need to develop a culture learning to obtain the knowledge base of the employees.

2.3 Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership is defined as a process of influencing major changes of the organisation's members (organisation culture) attitudes and assumptions, as well as building commitment for major changes in the objectives and strategies of the organisation (Yukl & Van Fleet, 1992). Transformational leaders primary concern is to effectively manage the major changes at the organisational level. These leaders understand that the major organisational changes at the individual and group levels depend on changing norms, values, assumptions and attitudes. Therefore, transformational leaders emphasise that to achieve goals, employee's attitude and values are important. The leaders also highlighted that when it is understood as a product of social capital and relationships, it shows how effective organisational change is.

It was argued that the development relationship between leaders and workers is parallel to the effective change in the organisational level (Burns, 1978). Thus, transformational leaders will foster subordinates and by linking the individuals interests to the collective interests, can move the subordinates beyond self-interests (Bass and Steidlmeier, 1999; Garcí'a-Morales et al., 2012; Gillespie and Mann, 2004).

There are four components of transformational style, namely idealised influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualised consideration (Bass, 1985). According to Nemanich and Keller (2007), idealised influence behavior transforms leaders into role models for their employees, helps them develop vision for the organisation and to follow ethical principles, encourages them to include risk-taking activities, and under uncertain environment, support employees to perform effectively. As for intellectual stimulation behavior, it stimulates an employees' intelligence to solve problems by analysing the job problems from different sides and discourages the use of traditional methods in order to solve problems. Inspirational motivation behavior, on the other hand, helps to achieve overall goals of the organisation by supporting leaders to use strategies to motivate and inspire employees (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Lastly, for individualised consideration, it transforms a leader into a mentor or coach for his/her employees and by providing equal opportunity to all employees, they support treating employees differently.

These four are important components in transformational leadership that supports KM by inspiring others to take risks and generate innovative solutions (Birasnav, 2014; Nemanich & Keller, 2007). Scholars often highlighted in the literature that charismatic leadership is a combination of idealized influence and inspirational motivation behaviors (Avolio, Bass, & Jung, 1999), while some quote that idealized influence alone represents charismatic leadership (Dubinsky, Yammarino, & Jolson, 1995). Birasnav (2014) showed that transformational leadership is a crucial role in facilitating knowledge acquisition, while Eom et al. (2015) stated that through intellectual stimulation that enhances knowledge sharing, transformational leaders can improve knowledge integration. Furthermore, it was found that transformational leadership built an environment that inspires others to share knowledge within the organisation (Lin & Hsiao, 2004).

2.4 Transformational Leaderships and KM

There have been many scholars who have empirically investigated the positive impacts transformational leadership has on individual performance and organisational performance. Correspondingly, KM scholars showcased the positive association between managing knowledge and organisational performance. According to Liebowitz and Beckman (1998), organisations discovered that by capturing, distributing, sharing, preserving, securing and valuing their precious knowledge, they would be able to stay ahead of their competition. McFarlane (2008) stated that within the knowledge economy, the transformation of the managers' insight strategic assets such as organisational knowledge is included. Knowledge plays a role as the critical resource in an organisation (Borghini, 2005; Venkitachalam & Busch, 2012), but it is the proper management of knowledge that enables organisations to enhance their competitiveness (Danskin et al., 2005; Grant, 1996; Wang et al., 2012).

Donate and Guadamillas (2011) and Singh (2008) stated that in an organisation, leadership plays an important role in managing knowledge within the organisation. If there is insufficient or ineffective support from top managers, it could lead to the failure of knowledge management projects (Davenport et al., 1998; Xue et al., 2011). According to Bryant (2003), it is essential to identify suitable leadership styles in this turbulent environment, as researchers have reported that varying leadership styles will have different impacts on the implementation of KM process. Of all the leadership theory, transformational leadership theory hypothesises that when leaders exhibit certain behaviors which accelerates employees' level of innovative thinking, it will help improve the employees performance, organisational innovation, and organisational performance (Aragon-Correa, Garcia-Morales, & Cordon-Pozo, 2007; Colbert, Kristof-Brown, Bradley, & Barrick, 2008; Piccolo & Colquitt, 2006). Thus, the role of transformational leadership focuses on the implementation of KM process in order to improve organisational performance.

Communities of practice theory can also be used as a base to understand the relationship between transformational leadership and KM. In the communities of practice, social learning in groups that share a common purpose in a particular domain, for example a firm or profession, is enabled. The core dynamics of community of practice is the mutual interest in learning and sharing knowledge with other members. It was described by Pemberton et al. (2007) that communities of practice are groups of like-minded people, whose correspondence requires a form of leadership that empowers employees with the freedom to discover new ideas and set its own agenda. Freeing employees from the shackles of organisational missives can be achieved with the commitment of the group members and facilitated by a leader, who also acts as a coordinator for the purpose of organising meetings.

As transformational leaders encourage the participation in social networks, Coakes and Smith (2007) found that this leadership is appropriate for building communities of practice for an innovative workplace where knowledge is shared. Corno et al. (2000) suggests that leaders need to create appropriate social architectures that will create a supportive environment for knowledge flow and enhance KM. This indicates that there is a relationship between transformational leadership and KM.

2.5 KM and Transformational Leadership lead to Positive Organisational Performance

KM is concerned about acquiring, integrating and sharing, and reconfiguring knowledge, while transformational leaders promote sharing practices that includes creating communities of

practice for learning and growth opportunities for employees. According to Khedhaouria and Jama (2015), in order to enhance organisational innovation and motivate employees to solve problems, it is good to generate new ideas and knowledge. Having a learning environment that empowers employees, enables an organisation to actively respond to changes in the environment and move employees by linking individual interests to the collective interests of the organisation, beyond self-interests (Bass and Steidlmeier, 1999). Additionally, to show concern for both organisations needs and employees' interests, transformational leaders employ individual consideration to identify employees' needs. Concern for employee's individual needs can contribute to an increase in organisational commitment that will inspire employees to work harder. This results in the improvements of the quality of products and services, as well as customer satisfaction which promotes higher returns on investment, and an opportunity to improve revenue by increasing sales or service.

An integration of knowledge is important as knowledge will be shared and synthesized in order to provide higher quality products and services (Lee & Kim, 2001). Both the integration of knowledge and the influence from transformational leaders positively impacts and improves financial and non-financial performances (greater customer focus, improved product and service quality, and increased sales). In addition, with knowledge reconfiguration, by developing interactions and awareness of the external environment, it will enable organisations to actively respond to environmental changes. From this, it can be seen that KM and transformational leadership has a positive relationship with organisational performance.

3 Alternative Solutions

By analysing the three articles, a few solutions will be suggested. The common problem of the three cases is related to the relevant knowledge of the specific organisation. Among others, in case study one about Sumbiling Eco Village (SEV), it was found that they had problems maintaining and repairing materials due to the weather and shortage of skilled workers. Besides that, they had a strong competition from nearby outbound retreats, which has shrunk their market, and lastly, the increase in visitors that could lead to environment degradation. In this case, training is very important to upgrade the workers skill. There are various ways in upgrading the skills, one of it is to employ an experienced worker from an established ecotourism industry, or they can make use of incentives, peer coaching, sending the staff to a related institution, or employ a consultant to train the staff. The employees can apply the new knowledge to improve the organisations as well as to help sustain and prolong the materials durability. With proper knowledge to manage and run the organisation, it will certainly lead to a more environmentally friendly ecosystem. However, in many cases, a well-trained employee is normally in high demand in other places. So, there is the disadvantage where the employees will leave the organisation after being trained. If this happens, the organisation does not only lose their investment, but in most cases, it will slow down their progress. The new cycle of retraining their employees will certainly use up the current resources. Besides that, an attractive incentive is important in order for skilled workers to remain longer within the organisation.

In case study two, BruTel have the dilemma in tackling their prospective senior citizen market. It was found that the senior citizen comprises of a high percentage of the population in this country. The identified problem with the senior citizen was that they are less receptive to technology. Aside from that, BruTel also faced losing potential customers from the general public

due to their cumbersome enrolment process as well as customers' password fatigue. In this situation, an outreach program should be given a priority. In order to prepare the staff for an outreach program, a proper in-depth training including various group psychology and needs is very important to be disseminated to the employees. Following that, the organisation should acquire the senior citizens demographics data so that they can prescribe the right solutions. This is important because the senior citizens consist of a diverse group, from illiterate to highly educated pensioners. To tackle them is not an easy task because the less educated might resist to technology, while the highly educated might think that they are capable. On a different note, customers' password fatigue and the cumbersome enrolment process is rampant among the society. Every individual is a potential customer for the organisation, and thus, user friendly applications should be prescribed. However, there are also disadvantage for these solutions where both solutions are time consuming and may lack resources, especially man power.

In case study three, SCOT's major challenge was the necessary funding for the organisation to expand its existing corporate social responsibility (CSR) project. For this case, the important thing is for the organisation to have an entrepreneurial knowledge. To sustain their organisation, an NGO, funding is always the key issue. Within their organisation structure, they should have an entrepreneurial department where its role and responsibility are to generate income for the organisation. However, the setback of this might be, they are too successful in business until they forget their main business of being an NGO.

4 Recommendations

Having the right knowledge in an organisation is vital for the organisation's growth and sustainability. However, various related knowledge, especially relating to the stakeholders is also very important. Managing this knowledge within the organisation is the leader's responsibility (Donate & Guadamillas, 2011; and Singh, 2008). For example, in case study one with SEV, proper understanding of the environment as well as biodegradable material to construct the building may seem unrelated to the core business and thus, they may not take this matter seriously. Nevertheless, leaders in this organisation are responsible to manage and apply this knowledge in order to sustain its core business. The organisation must commit to this in spite of its high cost maintenance, in order to avoid the possibility of destroying the environment.

On the issue of unskilled workers (BruTel and SEV), training employees is very important. Training can help improve an employee's job performance and employee development (Burden & Proctor, 2000), develop skills knowledge and attitudes (Al-Khayyat & Elgamal, 1997), and is a means of helping the organisation achieve a competitive edge (Hughey & Mussnug, 1997; Hallier & Butts, 2000). Training includes learning from experts of various organisations, peer coaching, consultants, or sending staff to related institutions. The knowledge they gain from this training can be used to improve the work process of the organisation as well as tackling various issues with regard to organisation operational matters. Due to the experience from other organisations that have been transferred to the employees, various unexpected problem and issues can be handled effectively. According to Auer (1995), the failure in providing such training can lead to an increase in failure, and costs more for the organisation in the long run.

Besides that, it is essential to retain trained and experienced staff, but not many organisations place the same emphasis or show the same commitment to this employee training (Roberts & McDonald, 1995; Hughey & Mussnug, 1997). Cappelli (2000) stated that some

organisations may work hard in recruiting the best people, but will spend little effort in trying to retain them once hired. It is said that by retaining these group of talented, productive, experienced and knowledgeable employees, can become a source of competitive advantage for organisations (King, 1997; Cheng & Brown, 1998; Roepke et al., 2000). According to Acton & Golden (2003), the retention of these employees, that aids in the retention of organisational knowledge (Cappelli, 2000), through continuous improvement practices, offers opportunities in raising quality standards (Motwani et al., 1994) and facilitating the achievement of a more consistent customer care (Rowley & Purcell, 2001), will provide them with staff stability. Some organisations believe that training is the key objective in increasing an employee's loyalty to the organisation as well as create a culture that emphasises the value of long-term employment (Acton & Golden, 2003), while some believe that an attractive incentive is better.

Furthermore, training can help develop an employee's innovation and creativity that can produce a unique product which provides a strategic advantage for the organisation. Thus, training and retraining is necessary for both an individual and an organisational growth (Read & Kleiner, 1996). Organisations working with the objective of a pay-off in terms of increased skill-sets, increased motivation, increased knowledge transfer (Pate et al., 2000), more positive psychological and organisational dynamics, as well as a measurable competitive edge, need to commit effort and finances to training programmes and employee development (Acton & Golden, 2003).

Just like any other NGOs, SCOT faces problems securing funds for its projects. In order to sustain the organisation, SCOT should create and implement a program that helps enable the organisation to become organisationally and financially sustainable, and thus, feasible for a long term (Alymkulova & Seipulnik, 2005). This program should include training employees to have an entrepreneurial knowledge. The organisation can then create a separate department consisting of these trained employees, who will focus on generating the funds needed for the organisation's projects, while the organisation focuses solely on its core business.

5 Conclusion

From the case studies, it is clear that the proper management of knowledge done by the organisations leaders plays an important role for the sustainability and effective management of an organisation. As an organisation expands and diversifies, most often, organisations do not possess the right skills and knowledge. In this knowledge economy, not properly managing knowledge can bring an organisation to failure. By having a learning environment that empowers employees, it enables an organisation to actively respond to changes in the environment, and by linking individual interests with the organisation's collective interests, can move employees beyond self-interests (Bass and Steidlmeier, 1999). When an organisations leader manage knowledge properly, they will be able to improve the quality of products and services, as well as customer satisfaction, which will then promote higher returns on investment, and an opportunity to improve revenue by increasing sales or service.

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